

RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

SIMOLES

Simulation and optimization of potential methods for valorization of lower quality wood in Slovenia

ARIS Targeted Research Programme CRP 2025

0 General Information	
0.1 Project code	V4-2512
0.2 Project title	Simulation and optimization of potential methods for valorization of lower quality wood in Slovenia (SIMOLES)
0.3 Project leader code	51616
0.4 Project leader	Dr. Balázs Dávid, InnoRenew CoE, Andrej Marušič Institute, University of Primorska (UP IAM IR) E-mail: balazs.david@innorenew.eu
0.5 Data steward / data management support	Dr. Ana Slavec provides institutional data management support as one of the data stewards of the University of Primorska. Participating organisation: University of Ljubljana, Biotechnical Faculty, Department of Wood Science (UL BF OL) — Dr. Primož Oven.
0.6 Institutional data management policy	Both UP IAM IR and UL BF OL follow internal data management regulations aligned with the Regulation on the implementation of scientific research work in accordance with the principles of open science (Official Gazette of RS, No. 59/23) and the ARIS open science policy.
0.7 RDMP version	Version 1.0.

1 Summary and Description of Research Data

<p>1.1 Will existing data from previous research be re-used?</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>Yes. The following existing data sources will be re-used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> National statistics on forest wood assortments, annual harvest, and material flows (GIS / Slovenia Forest Service, SURS, ZGS) Ecoinvent life cycle inventory database — for LCA background data on materials and processes Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs) from European databases — for comparative carbon footprint data Results and knowledge bases from prior related projects and research European forestry and industry statistics (e.g Eurostat, CEPI, EPF, CEI-Bois) <p>The above data will be used to provide input for LCA analyses in WP3 and the simulation model in WP4. No constraints on re-use are anticipated, except that proprietary third-party data (e.g. Ecoinvent, commercial EPDs) will not be redistributed — only derived, non-proprietary outputs will be shared.</p>
<p>1.2 What types and formats of data will be created or re-used?</p>	<p>Types of data by work package:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP2: Statistical and material-flow data on lower quality wood availability, harvest shares, and pricing along the forest-timber chain; qualitative inputs from stakeholder consultations in Slovenia and EEA countries; literature data on handling practices and good examples in the pan-European region; data on end-of-life and waste wood volumes and collection systems. WP3: Structured datasets describing reference processing plants (input/output materials, energy, labour, investment costs, profitability); Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) data for selected wood and non-wood products (carbon footprint, GHG emissions, environmental impact metrics); profitability matrix combining economic, technical and environmental performance indicators. WP4: Outputs of the Discrete Event Simulation (DES) model of end-of-life wood flows (Used Wood Model); scenario datasets with economic and environmental results (GHG savings, substitution effects, sequestration effects) under multiple policy assumptions. <p>Data formats:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> CSV — structured tabular data (material flows, survey results, LCA indicators, profitability matrices, scenario outputs). Preferred open format for long-term preservation and interoperability. XLSX — working datasets and model input tables during active project phases. DOCX / PDF — reports, stakeholder consultation documentation, policy recommendations. <p>Open formats (CSV, PDF) are preferred for final deposits to ensure long-term accessibility and repository compatibility.</p>
<p>1.3 What is the purpose of data creation / collection / re-use and its connection to project objectives?</p>	<p>Data are created and collected to achieve the specific project objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> C1–C3: Analysis of lower quality wood availability and handling practices in Slovenia, EEA countries, and countries with good practices — requiring statistical data, material flow data, and stakeholder survey data (WP2). C4–C5: Preparation of a product proposal and profitability matrix for lower quality wood processing — requiring LCA data, plant parameters, and economic data (WP3). C6–C8: Development of the Integrated National Model and scenario analysis of economic and environmental impacts — requiring updated knowledge bases, simulation outputs, and scenario data (WP4).
<p>1.4 Expected data volume</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 0–10 GB <input type="checkbox"/> 10–100 GB <input type="checkbox"/> 100–1000 GB <input type="checkbox"/> >1000 GB</p>

2 Data Storage and Backup

<p>2.1 Where will data be stored and backed up during the project?</p>	<p>During the project, data will be stored on institutionally approved storage services of UP IAM IR and UL BF OL (e.g., Microsoft Teams and OneDrive). Automatic backup is managed by such services.</p> <p>For collaborative data exchange between partners, the same secure cloud-based platforms may be used. Final processed datasets will be deposited in the Zenodo repository at the time of or shortly after publication whenever possible.</p>
<p>2.2 How will data be selected for long-term preservation?</p>	<p>The following data will be selected for long-term preservation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Final versions of all deposited datasets • Analysis scripts and code (version-controlled via Git or equivalent)
<p>2.3 Will data be stored in a trusted repository?</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>Yes. Data will be deposited in Zenodo (https://zenodo.org) — for datasets, code, and supplementary materials linked to publications.</p>

3 Making Data Available in a FAIR Manner	
3.1 Ensuring Findability (F)	
3.1.1 Will data be assigned a persistent identifier (PID)?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No Yes. Each dataset deposited in Zenodo will be assigned a DOI (Digital Object Identifier).
3.1.2 What metadata will be created and which metadata standards will be applied?	Metadata will follow established standards: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dublin Core — for general datasets (title, creator, subject, description, publisher, date, type, format, identifier, source, language, relation, coverage, rights).
3.1.3 Will metadata include keywords to improve findability and re-use potential?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No Yes. Metadata will include carefully selected keywords to maximise discoverability. Keywords will be drawn from controlled vocabularies used by the research community and will be aligned with established thesauri including AGROVOC (FAO) and EuroVoc (EU)
3.2 Ensuring Accessibility (A)	
3.2.1 Will all data be openly accessible?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No Not all data will be fully open access. Restrictions apply in the following cases: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proprietary third-party data (Ecoinvent database, commercial EPDs): these will not be redistributed. Only derived, non-proprietary outputs (e.g. calculated carbon footprint values, aggregated results) will be shared openly. • Private data from stakeholder consultations: For all other data produced by the project, open access under CC BY 4.0 is the default.
3.2.2 When will data be openly accessible and for how long?	If possible, data will be made openly accessible at the time of, or shortly after, publication of associated scientific or professional outputs. Internal research data and data underpinning published scientific articles will be retained on institutional servers for a minimum of 5 years after project completion in accordance with institutional policies.
3.2.3 How will access be enabled in the case of use restrictions?	For data subject to access restrictions, the following mechanisms apply: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Private and proprietary third-party data: not shared; users directed to original source providers. If possible, metadata for datasets will be openly accessible without restriction, allowing discovery of all project data regardless of access conditions.
3.2.4 Will additional documentation or information about suitable software be needed to access or read the data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No Yes. For certain data types, specific software will be required: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Python / R scripts: require standard Python and/or R installations
3.3 Ensuring Interoperability (I)	
3.3.1 Which thesauri or code lists will be used in preparing data and metadata?	The following controlled vocabularies and thesauri will be applied: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AGROVOC (FAO) and EuroVoc

<p>3.3.2 Will less well-known or proprietary thesauri / code lists be used?</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>3.4 Ensuring Re-usability (R)</p>	
<p>3.4.1 How will documentation necessary for re-use of data be ensured?</p>	<p>Each dataset deposited in a repository will be accompanied by a README file (plain text, TXT format) containing as a minimum:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description of dataset content and file structure • Data collection methodology (model description, LCA system boundaries) • Variable descriptions and units of measurement • Software and versions used to produce or analyse the data • Pre-processing and cleaning steps applied • Access conditions and licence • Contact details of the responsible person
<p>3.4.2 Will data be publicly available and licensed under CC BY or CC BY-SA to enable the widest possible re-use?</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>Yes. Wherever possible, project-generated datasets will be published under CC BY 4.0 (Creative Commons Attribution).</p>
<p>3.4.3 What data quality assurance procedures will be used?</p>	<p>The following quality assurance measures will be applied throughout the project:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cross-validation of statistical input data against multiple independent sources (SURS, GIS / Slovenia Forest Service, Eurostat) to identify inconsistencies. • peer review of modelling results and scenario assumptions before finalisation (WP3, WP4). • Version control of all model scripts and knowledge base files using Git (GitHub)

4 Ethical and Legal Aspects	
4.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that could affect data sharing?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No The project does not involve the collection of personal data from human participants.
4.2 Will personal data be processed or stored during the project?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No The project does not involve the collection of personal data from human participants.
4.3 Will special categories of personal data be created or re-used during the project?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No The project does not involve the collection of personal data from human participants.
4.4 How will data ownership and any copyright over created or re-used data be managed?	Data ownership follows the institutional policies of each partner organisation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data collected and generated by UP IAM IR are owned by UP IAM IR. • Data collected and generated by UL BF OL are owned by UL BF OL. • Jointly produced datasets are under joint ownership of both partner institutions.

5 Other Research Outputs

5.1 Will other research outputs besides data be created or re-used?

- Yes
- No

Yes. The following other research outputs will be produced:

Digital outputs (software and models):

- Used Wood Model— discrete event simulation of end-of-life wood flows across Slovenia. If open-source, published on GitHub/Zenodo.

Scientific publications:

- Peer-reviewed scientific articles in international open-access journals
- Professional publications and conference contributions

All outputs will be shared and made available for re-use in accordance with FAIR principles whenever possible, with open-access publication as the default.

6 Financial Resources

<p>6.1 What are the costs of managing data and other project outputs according to FAIR principles, and how will they be covered?</p>	<p>The only costs we anticipate for data management are personnel costs, which we have already been taken into account when preparing the research proposal. There will be no storage costs, as we will submit the data to repositories that are available to researchers free of charge.</p>
<p>6.2 Who is the responsible person for data management in the project?</p>	<p>Balázs Dávid</p>

Version History

Version	Date	Description
1.0	2026	Initial version